

Two-mode dissipation of oscillating tuning fork in ^3He – ^4He superfluid mixtures

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In this paper, we present the results of theoretical studies of the possible mechanism of energy dissipation that takes place in the experiments with vibrating quartz fork in superfluid ^3He – ^4He mixtures with high concentration. The possibility and efficiency of the tuning fork radiation of both the second sound wave and the diffusion dissipative wave were investigated. The relationships between the amplitudes of temperature and concentration oscillations in these waves were found and the relative wave intensities were determined. This allowed us to give a possible explanation for observed additional mechanisms of tuning fork attenuation in helium solutions.

Keywords: energy dissipation, helium solution, temperature and concentration oscillations, second sound wave, diffusion dissipative wave.

Introduction

The tuning fork has been and remains not only an object of intensive research but also a method for determining the characteristics of helium [1–26] like viscosity, sound velocity, nonlinear motion, cavitation, etc. At the same time, although most experimentally observed phenomena received a fairly correct theoretical description, there are some of them that still remain unexplained. For example, in pure helium, the tuning fork attenuation and frequency change were described in sufficient detail [3–5]. Taking into account the generation of the first sound and viscous friction allowed describing the observed properties of the tuning fork at different temperatures and for a fairly wide range of tuning fork sizes and frequencies [4–10]. However, in the case of a solution, such a satisfactory agreement could not be obtained [1, 2].

In this paper, we present a theoretical study of the possible mechanisms of energy dissipation that takes place in the experiments [1–3] of a vibrating quartz fork in superfluid ^3He – ^4He mixtures with high concentration.

Recall that experiments [1, 2] were conducted under different conditions: on a closed and open tuning fork and in solutions with different concentrations and temperatures.

They showed the presence of additional damping and taking into account collective mode, namely, the second sound, gave contradictory results in the interpretation of these experiments.

In this work, we consider the fact that in superfluid solutions, unlike pure helium, concentration and temperature disturbances relax and propagate through the solution by two physical mechanisms. One of them is the second sound, which in pure helium causes the evolution of temperature and entropy. The second mechanism is a diffusion dissipative wave, which is unique for solutions [27–30].

Set-up of equations

To begin, we give expressions [27–30] for the relaxation of the initial delta-shaped relative temperature perturbation for temperature

$$T(x, t) = \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_2^2} G_{D_{\text{eff}}}(x, t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} (G^{(+)}(x, t) + G^{(-)}(x, t)) \quad (1)$$

and for concentration

$$c(x, t) = \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} \frac{c_p}{\bar{\sigma}} \left[\frac{1}{2} (G^{(+)}(x, t) + G^{(-)}(x, t)) - G_{D_{\text{eff}}}(x, t) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Here, relatively small changes in temperature and concentration with respect to their equilibrium values $T(x, t) = \delta T(x, t) / T_0$ and $c(x, t) = \delta c(x, t) / c_0$ are introduced.

In obtaining these results, we used the relationships between the amplitudes of temperature and concentration oscillations in the second sound wave [31–35]

$$c(x, t) = T(x, t) \frac{c_p}{\bar{\sigma}} \quad (3)$$

and in the dissipative diffusion wave

$$c(x, t) = -\frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_{2N}^2} \frac{c_p}{\bar{\sigma}} T(x, t). \quad (4)$$

Here, $u_2^2 = u_{2\varepsilon}^2 + u_{2N}^2$ is the squared value of the second sound velocity [31], c_p is the heat capacity, $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma - c\partial\sigma/\partial c$, and σ is the entropy of the mixture. In Eqs. (1), (2), we used the Green function

$$G_{D_{\text{eff}}}(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi D_{\text{eff}} t}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{4D_{\text{eff}} t}\right), \quad (5)$$

that describes the relaxation due to the dissipative mechanism of effective diffusion and the functions

$$G_S^{(\pm)}(x, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi\Gamma_s t}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x \pm u_2 t)^2}{4\Gamma_s t}\right) \quad (6)$$

that describe the relaxation caused by the propagation of the second sound. Here, Γ_s is the absorption coefficient of the second sound,

$$\Gamma_s = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\kappa}{c_p} \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} + D \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_2^2} \left(1 + \frac{k_T \bar{\sigma}}{C_V c_0} \right)^2 \right) \quad (7)$$

and

$$D_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\kappa}{c_p} \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_2^2} + D \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} \left(1 - k_T \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{c_0 c_p} \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_{2\varepsilon}^2} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

is the effective diffusion coefficient, where κ , D , and k_T are coefficients of thermal conductivity, diffusion, and thermal diffusion ratio, respectively.

Now, let us present expressions for the evolution of concentration:

$$c(x, t) = \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} G_{D_{\text{eff}}}(x, t) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_2^2} \left(G^{(+)}(x, t) + G^{(-)}(x, t) \right) \quad (9)$$

and temperature

$$T(x, t) = \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_2^2} \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{c_p} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(G^{(+)}(x, t) + G^{(-)}(x, t) \right) - G_{D_{\text{eff}}}(x, t) \right] \quad (10)$$

in the case of the initial delta-shape concentration disturbance.

From Eqs. (9), (10) and (1), (2), it follows that the relative contribution of each of these modes to relaxation depends significantly on the parameters of the solution, namely temperature and concentration. Thus, at very low concentrations and sufficiently high temperatures, when the properties of the solution are close to the properties of pure helium, the entropy relaxes in the second-sound wave, and the impurities relax through the dissipative diffusion mode. In the opposite case of sufficiently low temperatures and sufficiently high concentrations, the situation can be the opposite, when temperature perturbations relax through the diffusion mode (in a dissipative thermal wave), and the concentration relaxes in the second sound wave.

In particular, in solutions with a concentration of 15% and temperatures from 0.4 to 1.5 K, which were studied in works [1–3], a situation is realized in which the relative contributions of the two modes become of the same order.

Two problems with boundary conditions

To study the oscillating tuning fork in such solutions, we move from the problem of the evolution of a delta-shaped initial disturbance, which is necessary for studying arbitrary initial disturbances, to the problem of collective mode radiation (and further propagation) by solid boundary under given boundary conditions that are periodic in time.

As the first problem, we consider radiation by a wall at a point $x = 0$, the temperature of which changes according to a periodic law

$$T(x = 0) = \tilde{T} e^{-i\omega t}, \quad (11)$$

and the concentration at the boundary is not disturbed

$$c(x = 0) = 0. \quad (12)$$

Then, for the region $x > 0$ the distributions of temperature and concentration in the solution are given by the relations:

$$T(x, t) = \tilde{T} \left\{ \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} e^{ik_2 x} + \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_2^2} e^{-\frac{x}{\delta_D}(1+i)} \right\} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (13)$$

and

$$c(x, t) = \frac{c_p}{\bar{\sigma}} \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} \tilde{T} \left\{ e^{ik_2 x} - e^{-\frac{x}{\delta_D}(1+i)} \right\} e^{-i\omega t}. \quad (14)$$

Here, $k_2 = \omega / u_2$ is the wave vector of the second sound and

$$\delta_D = \sqrt{\frac{2D_{\text{eff}}}{\omega}} \quad (15)$$

is the penetration depth or wavelength of the dissipative diffusion wave.

These relations are obtained from the known relations between the amplitudes of concentration and temperature

in these modes Eqs. (3), (4) and the boundary conditions Eqs. (11), (12).

In the case of a solid wall with an oscillating temperature, it is more natural to consider other physical boundary conditions. We should ensure the absence of impurity flow at the boundary. If we consider only the mass diffusion, we get the condition for the derivative

$$c'(x=0) = 0. \quad (16)$$

In this case, we obtain the following result for the temperature and concentration:

$$T(x,t) = \tilde{T} \left\{ e^{ik_2x} - i \frac{u_{2N}^2 k_2 \delta_D}{u_{2\varepsilon}^2 (1+i)} e^{-\frac{x}{\delta_D}(1+i)} \right\} e^{-i\omega t} \quad (17)$$

and

$$c(x,t) = \frac{c_p}{\bar{c}} \tilde{T} \left\{ e^{ik_2x} + \frac{ik_2 \delta_D}{1+i} e^{-\frac{x}{\delta_D}(1+i)} \right\} e^{-i\omega t}. \quad (18)$$

From these relations, it follows that a dissipative wave is also emitted simultaneously with the second sound. The efficiency of its emission is determined by the ratio of the wavelengths of the second sound and the diffusion wave:

$$k_2 \delta_D = \frac{\omega}{u_2} \delta_D = \frac{2\pi \delta_D}{\lambda_2}. \quad (19)$$

We will consider possible relationships between the radiation efficiencies of these waves for the specific case of experiments with an oscillating tuning fork below.

As a second problem, we consider the radiation of a diffusion mode and second sound by an oscillating wall with a given velocity of oscillation of the boundary, as is the case in a tuning fork.

In this case, we should use boundary conditions on the flow of impurities (16) and the velocities of the normal v_n and superfluid v_s components of helium

$$v_n(x=0) = v_s(x=0) = V_0 e^{-i\omega t}. \quad (20)$$

Here, V_0 is the amplitude of the wall oscillation.

With this formulation of the problem, we can determine the radiation efficiency of all three modes: the first sound, the second sound, and the diffusion wave. Recall that the problem of simultaneous radiation of the first and second sound in pure helium and solutions was solved in Refs. 33, 34.

Tuning fork damping

In this work, we consider the simultaneous radiation of three modes to examine their contribution to the damping of the oscillating tuning forks. For this, we use the known relationships between the amplitudes of hydrodynamic quantities in the first and second sound waves Refs. 33, 34.

and take into account relationships (3) and (4) in the dissipative diffusion wave. From the boundary conditions (16) and (20), we obtain the following expressions for the temperature and concentration disturbances caused by the oscillating solid wall:

$$T(x,t) = -\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_n} \frac{V_0}{\bar{c}} \frac{\bar{c}}{u_2 c_p} \times \left\{ \frac{u_2}{u_1} e^{ik_1x} + e^{ik_2x} - \delta_D k_2 \frac{1+i}{2} \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_{2\varepsilon}^2} e^{-\frac{x}{\delta_D}(1+i)} \right\}, \quad (21)$$

and

$$c(x,t) = -\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_n} \frac{V_0}{\bar{c}} \frac{1}{u_2} \left\{ \frac{u_2}{u_1} e^{ik_1x} + e^{ik_2x} + \delta_D k_2 \frac{1+i}{2} e^{-\frac{x}{\delta_D}(1+i)} \right\}. \quad (22)$$

Here, $k_1 = \omega / u_1$ is the wave vector of the first sound. The value

$$\bar{c} = \frac{c}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial c} \right)_{T,P} \quad (23)$$

determines the ‘‘mixing’’ of the first and second sounds and can have fairly large values in solutions, unlike pure helium, where the coupling of sounds is determined by a very small coefficient of thermal expansion.

The relationships (21) and (22) allow us to compare the radiation intensities of the first and second sounds for radiation from an infinite flat solid wall and get the well-known results [31, 33]

$$\frac{I_2}{I_1} = \bar{c}^2 \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_n} \frac{u_2}{u_1}. \quad (24)$$

With such a geometry of the emitter, the efficiency of radiation of the second sound and the diffusion mode is certainly small compared to the first sound. At the same time, for an oscillating tuning fork, the sound radiation intensities (acoustic draft) are determined essentially by other relationships, which are due to the complex shape of the tuning fork. For example, a typical expression for the relative broadening of the resonance curve of acoustic drag in the long-wave limit of the so-called two-dimensional tuning fork model has the form [14, 16]:

$$\frac{\Delta f_a^{(2D)}}{f_0} = C_{2D} \frac{\rho}{m_{\text{eff}}} W^2 L_e \frac{3}{64} \left(\frac{2\pi f_0}{u} \right)^4 T^2 (T+D)^2. \quad (25)$$

Here, the quantity m_{eff} is the effective mass of the tuning fork in helium, W , L_e , T , and D are the values that are determined by the size and shape of the tuning fork, C_{2D} is the geometric form-factor of the order of unity, f_0 is the frequency of the tuning fork.

We see that this value is inversely proportional to the fourth power of the speed of sound. In this regard, as was shown in Refs. 1, 2, the contribution of the second

sound to damping can be compared and even prevail over the contribution of the first sound. Equation (25) was obtained in [14, 15] for the case of the first sound emission by a tuning fork in pure helium. A similar expression for the emission due to the second sound emission has not been derived either for pure helium or for mixtures. That is, Eq. (25) can be used only for qualitative reasoning (for example, from dimensionality considerations) regarding the contribution of the first and second sounds to theacoustical drag of the tuning fork. Such reasoning was, in particular, given in Ref. 1 (Eq. 8) for a possible description of the fact observed in the experiment that the contribution of second sound to damping can be compared and even prevail over the contribution of first sound.

At the same time, in these Refs. 1, 2, a difference was found in the behavior of an open tuning fork and a closed tuning fork, which was in a fairly small flask. It turned out that the attenuation of an open tuning fork is greater than that of a closed one. This phenomenon can be explained in particular if we assume that in a closed tuning fork, unlike an open one, a wave of the second sound is not formed in the wave zone.

The point is that the dimensions of the flask do not differ significantly from the wavelength of the second sound, and we can assume that the quasi-plane wave of the second sound is not formed. In this case, the excess attenuation can be caused by the radiation of only the dissipative mode. To estimate the efficiency of losses in the diffusion mode in comparison with the second sound, we use Eqs. (21), (22). From them, it follows that, to the extent of the ratio $u_2/u_1 \ll 1$, both temperature and concentration are mainly relaxing in the wave of the second sound and in the diffusion wave but not in the first sound wave. The relative contribution of these modes to the fork damping is determined by the following relation:

$$\frac{I_D}{I_2} = \frac{2\pi\delta_D}{\lambda_2} \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}. \quad (26)$$

Let us present the calculations of the ratio (26) for solutions that were studied in the Refs. 1, 2 for solutions with a concentration of 15% and for temperatures from 0.5 to 1.4 K. As an expression for the effective diffusion coefficient D_{eff} [8] under these conditions, the following can be used

$$D_{\text{eff}} = D \frac{u_{2\varepsilon}^2}{u_2^2} \left(1 + \frac{m_3^* u_1^2}{k_B T} \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{c_P} \frac{u_{2N}^2}{u_{2\varepsilon}^2} \right)^2. \quad (27)$$

The mass diffusion coefficient D can be determined from theory [36] or directly from the experimental results [37].

From the figure, it is clear that in the entire temperature range for a concentration of 15%, the contributions of the second sound radiation intensities and the diffusion wave were of the same order. So, we can conclude that the excess in comparison with viscous friction and acoustic

Fig. 1. The temperature dependence of the ratio of the intensities of the diffusion mode to second sound (26) for a mixture of 15% of ^3He .

friction of the tuning fork in solutions in a closed tuning fork can be caused by the diffusion mode, and in an open tuning fork, by the emission of the second sound and a diffusion wave. To confirm this assumption, it is necessary to consider the problem of tuning fork oscillations in a sufficiently narrow cylindrical flask and consider all possible collective modes of superfluid solutions of ^3He - ^4He .

Finally, in this paper, the explicit expressions for the amplitudes of concentration and temperature perturbations caused by oscillations of a solid wall in helium are derived for the first time. The obtained relations, in particular, allow us to determine the region of temperatures and concentrations where the contribution of the diffusion mode to energy emission can be comparable to the contribution of the second sound. In particular, it turned out that experiments on the study of tuning fork attenuation in solutions were carried out in such a region. The calculations carried out in the work confirmed that the difference in the attenuation of open and closed tuning forks observed in the experiment (give reference) can be caused by the suppression of the second sound radiation and the presence of a diffusion dissipative wave.

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Дворежимне затухання коливань камертона у надплинних розчинах ^3He - ^4He

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Представлено результати теоретичних досліджень можливого механізму дисипації енергії, що відбувається в експериментах з кварцовим камертоном, який коливається в надплинних розчинах ^3He - ^4He з високою концентрацією. Досліджено можливість та ефективність випромінювання камертоном як хвилі другого звуку, так і дифузійної дисипативної хвилі. Знайдено зв'язки між амплітудами коливань температури та концентрації в цих хвилях і визначено відносні інтенсивності хвиль. Це дозволило дати можливе пояснення спостережуваних додаткових механізмів послаблення коливань камертона в розчинах ізотопів гелію.

Ключові слова: розсіювання енергії, розчин гелію, коливання температури та концентрації, хвиля другого звуку, дифузійна дисипативна хвиля.